

Exploring Tourist Demographics, Travel Preferences, And Promotional Influences In Jammu And Kashmir: A Quantitative Analysis

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Abstract

This study explores the demographic characteristics, travel motivations, and awareness levels of tourists visiting Jammu and Kashmir, based on a sample of 450 respondents. With the region emerging as a significant destination in India's tourism landscape, understanding visitor profiles and preferences is vital for strategic tourism planning. The research reveals that a majority of the tourists were domestic (75.8%), predominantly male (65.3%), and mostly within the 26–45 age group. Married individuals formed a greater proportion of travelers compared to single individuals. Hindus comprised the largest religious group, and most visitors held at least a graduate-level education. In terms of travel purpose, recreation and pilgrimage emerged as primary motivations, with many tourists staying for 3–5 nights and traveling mostly with family or friends. Notably, digital platforms such as online marketing and event-based promotions were the most influential in shaping travel decisions, while traditional direct marketing strategies like kiosk and mail-based promotions had minimal impact. The findings highlight the need for targeted marketing strategies and better infrastructure to support diverse tourist needs in Jammu and Kashmir.

Keywords

Jammu and Kashmir, Education, Tourism, Traveling, Awareness.

Introduction

Businesses such as hotels, airlines, cruise lines, car rental agencies, tour operators, etc., are the backbone of the tourist industry. The only thing they have in common is that they entail planning for events that individuals will be participating in in locations other than where they normally dwell. Tourism is the sum of the industries and activities that provide visitors with a pleasant experience while they are away from home. These industries and activities include transportation, lodging, food and drink services, shopping, entertainment, and recreational opportunities. [1]

Tourism is unique in that it incorporates many of the economy's other productive sectors, including agriculture, major and small enterprises, transportation, communication, lodging, and entertainment, among many others. Hospitality and transportation are the two key sectors that make up the tourist industry. Tourism is a major industry and source of revenue, jobs, and foreign currency for many poorer nations. The number of tourists traveling abroad from developing nations is on the rise, and between 2000 and 2006, their spending abroad increased by a factor of two.[2]

It is well acknowledged that tourism can be a powerful tool for economic growth and job creation, especially in underdeveloped regions. U.N. delegates at the Rome Conference on International Travel and Tourism in 1963 recognized tourism's value not just as a source of revenue but also as a driver of progress in underprivileged areas.[3]

Objective of study

This study explores the demographic characteristics, travel motivations, and awareness levels of tourists visiting Jammu and Kashmir.

Review of Literature

The potential for tourism in India is enormous. It has terrains such as mountains, forests, rivers, and oceans. Wildlife and the country's abundance of historic sites are two of India's most popular tourist draws. Ellora, Elephanta, Khajuraho, Khandagiri, Udagiri, and Tanjore are home to ancient Hindu temples and caverns that include priceless artifacts including statues, paintings, and relics from Buddha's time. The exquisite Tajmahal, as well as the monuments, palaces, and forts built during the Muslim era (such as those in Goa, Diu, and Bandel) and the remnants of European rule (such as those in Chennai, Surat, Lucknow, and the Himalayas) are all popular destinations for visitors. [4]

India occupies much of southern Asia. There is a peninsula in the south of the nation. The culture of India is quite varied. Its appearance is complex and multifaceted. There are five main geographic regions in the nation.[5] The Himalayas, the Indo-Gangetic plain, the Brahmaputra Valley, the Deccan plateau in southern India, the Great Indian Desert, and the coastal plains all make to India's varied topography.[6]

Jammu and Kashmir is one of India's northern states, and its territory, without considering the territory now controlled by Pakistan and China, is 10,1387 square kilometers (3.2% of India's total land area). The Chinese mainland and the Indian states of Punjab and Himachal Pradesh form its northern and eastern borders, respectively. [7] Jammu, Kashmir, and Ladakh are its three separate areas. The State of J&K has become a popular vacation spot for people from all over the world due to its abundance of natural beauty, mild year-round temperatures, unique social and cultural values, abundant wildlife, abundant water life, and numerous protected areas and sanctuaries. [8] Due to differences in terrain, temperature, and position, each of the state's three regions offers a unique opportunity for tourism growth. In the Kashmir valley, visitors come to relax and enjoy the scenery, in Jammu, the "City of Temples," visitors come to worship, and in Ladakh, visitors come to experience the region's rich culture and to try their hand at activities like climbing, hiking, and rafting.[9]

Kashmir valley is home to some of the world's most exquisite tourist attractions. It offers world-class skiing for adventurers, beautiful scenery for artists and ordinary people, rugged terrain perfect for hiking and mountaineering, a plethora of plant life for botanists, uncharted territory for geologists, ancient ruins for archaeologists, a rainbow of avian species for ornithologists, and delicious fruits and vegetables for gourmands.[10]

Methodology

A quantitative, descriptive research design was employed for this study to assess the demographic characteristics, travel objectives, and promotional influences affecting tourists visiting Jammu and Kashmir. The data was collected through a structured questionnaire administered to 450 tourists, comprising both domestic (n=341) and international (n=109) visitors. The sample was selected using a purposive sampling technique to ensure representation across different nationalities, genders, age groups, marital statuses, religions, educational backgrounds, and income brackets. The questionnaire included both closed-ended and Likert-scale-based questions, designed to measure tourists' travel motivations, duration of stay, group composition, and awareness generated through various promotional methods. Data were statistically analyzed using descriptive tools such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations. Promotional tools were ranked based on their mean effectiveness scores, revealing that digital and event-based strategies had the highest impact, while traditional direct marketing performed poorly. The methodology ensured a robust understanding of both the profile of tourists and the strategic effectiveness of current tourism promotional practices in the region.

Result and Discussion

Evaluation of demographic factors is crucial for getting an accurate picture of the tourist potential of Jammu and Kashmir's different destinations. Various demographic factors have been included in this area of the research, including nationality, sex, age, marital status, religion, education, employment status, and monthly income. The features of each component have been described using tables and bar graphs.

From a total of 450 responses, 341 were from inside India (or domestic tourists), making up 75.8% of the total, while 109 were from outside the country (or foreign tourists), making up 24.4%. This information is shown in the table below.

Table 1: Local vs International Travellers

	Indian		Foreigner		Total	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
Respondents	341	75.8%	109	24.4%	450	100.0%

Males made up 65.3% of the total, with 50.9% being Indian and 14.4% being foreigners, as can be seen in the table below. There were a total of 34.7% females, with 24.9% being Indian and 9.8% being foreigners.

Table 2: Divorce and Nationality

Characteristic/ Profile	Indian		Foreigner		Total	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
Male	229	50.9%	65	14.4%	294	65.3%
Female	112	24.9%	44	9.8%	156	34.7%
Total	341	75.8%	109	24.2%	450	100.0%

Just looking at the statistics for the age group '26-35' accounted for the most responders (53.9%), followed by the '36-45' age group. Among the total responders, 12.2% were of retirement age (defined as 55 and above), with 10.2% being Indian and 9.1% being foreigners making up the smallest proportion.

The '46-55' age group accounted for 19.3% of the total, with 46 Indians and 41 foreigners making up that group. The second-lowest proportion was among respondents younger than 26 years old (15.6%), with the majority being Indians (15.1%) and just 0.4% being foreigners.

Table 3: Differences in Nationality and Age

Characteristic/ Profile	Indian		Foreigner		Total	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
Less than 26 years	68	15.1%	2	0.4%	70	15.6%
26-35 years	98	21.8%	22	4.9%	120	26.7%
36-45 years	91	20.2%	27	6.0%	118	26.2%
46-55 years	46	10.2%	41	9.1%	87	19.3%
Above 55 years	38	8.4%	17	3.8%	55	12.2%
Total	341	75.8%	109	24.2%	450	100.0%

The proportion of married visitors is somewhat larger than the percentage of unmarried tourists, as can be seen from the underlying table. The majority of responders (58.9%) were married tourists; among them, 40.0% were Indian and 18.95 were from other countries. Of all tourists, 41.1% were travelling alone; this included 35.8% Indians and 5.3% international visitors.

Table 4: Comparison of Nationality and Marital Status

Characteristic/ Profile	Indian		Foreigner		Total	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
Single	161	35.8%	24	5.3%	185	41.1%
Married	180	40.0%	85	18.9%	265	58.9%
Total	341	75.8%	109	24.2%	450	100.0%

With 225 out of 450 respondents (or 50% of the total), 207 of whom were Indian and 18 of whom were foreigners, the accompanying table and image make it quite evident that Hindus made up the biggest part of the respondents. As a result of the many holy sites in Jammu and Kashmir, the proportion of Hindus to the overall population is disproportionately large. Hindus also make up a significant portion of the responders since their total population is larger than that of other religious groups. Muslims made up 22.4% of the total responders, with 22.2% being Indian visitors and 0.2% being overseas tourists. There was only one Muslim foreigner among the responders; he came with some Indian buddies. During the data collecting period, no Sikh from outside of India visited Jammu and Kashmir. However, 4.2% of Sikhs from India visited the region, with the majority of these visitors coming for leisure, adventure, or enjoyment. With 18.4% of the overall responders and 76.14% of the total foreign visitors identifying as Christians, the majority of the foreigners that visited were of Christian belief. They came largely to learn about the history and culture of Jammu and Kashmir's many attractions, but others also came for relaxation and health-related pursuits like yoga. A mere 2.7% of the total respondents identified as Buddhist. Members of the Jewish, Parsi, and non-believer communities, who were all foreign nationals, made up the smallest percentage of the total, 0.9%.

Table 5: Religious Belief vs. Nationality

Characteristic/ Profile	Indian		Foreigner		Total	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
Hindu	207	46.0%	18	4.0%	225	50.0%
Muslim	100	22.2%	1	0.2%	101	22.4%
Sikh	19	4.2%	0	0.0%	19	4.2%
Christian	6	1.3%	83	18.4%	89	19.8%
Buddhist	9	2.0%	3	0.7%	12	2.7%
Other	0	0.0%	4	0.9%	4	0.9%
Total	341	75.8%	109	24.2%	450	100.0%

Among the total respondents, 61.1% were graduates; of this group, 48.2% were Indian and 12.9% were from other countries. This information is shown in the table below. Of the total number of visitors, 23.6% were postgraduates; of this group, 20% were Indian and 3.6% were from other countries.

As far as educational qualifications go, 11.6% of visitors fell into the technical group. In terms of higher education, just 2% of visitors (1.1% of Indians and 0.9% of foreigners) have earned a Ph.D., M.Phil, etc. The high school group made the least contribution, at 1.8%. This data demonstrates that the majority of visitors were able to read and write well enough to intelligently complete the surveys.

Table 6: Educational Opportunity vs. Nationality

Characteristic/ Profile	Indian		Foreigner		Total	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
High school	6	1.3%	2	0.4%	8	1.8%
Graduate	217	48.2%	58	12.9%	275	61.1%
Post graduate	90	20.0%	16	3.6%	106	23.6%
Higher	5	1.1%	4	0.9%	9	2.0%
Technical	23	5.1%	29	6.4%	52	11.6%
Total	341	75.8%	109	24.2%	450	100.0%

The most prominent group is leisure, which included 116 Indians and 19 foreigners, accounting for 25.8% and 4.2% of the total, respectively, according to the statistics and the photo included below. Twenty-22.2% of respondents, 96 of whom were Indian and 4 of whom were foreigners, cited a pleasure vacation as the second most significant reason for their visit. Of the total number of pilgrims who made the journey, 15.8% were foreigners and 10.9% were Indians. Ten percent of all respondents said that learning about the destination's culture and history was the main reason they travelled there. Both "official visit" and "visiting friends and relatives" accounted for 1.6% of the total responses, making them the least significant category. The adventure tourism subset accounted for 5.6% of the total, with 24 out of 25 visitors being Indian and 1 being from another country. Business made up 2.4%, education 3.3%, and health care 4.0%. A small percentage of respondents (1.8%) chose their honeymoon as the reason for their trip.

Table 7: Differences in Nationality and Visit Objectives

Characteristic/ Profile	Indian		Foreigner		Total	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
Business	10	2.2%	1	0.2%	11	2.4%
Pleasure trip	96	21.3%	4	0.9%	100	22.2%
Official	7	1.6%	0	0.0%	7	1.6%
Education	14	3.1%	4	0.9%	18	4.0%
Pilgrimage	49	10.9%	22	4.9%	71	15.8%
Recreation	116	25.8%	19	4.2%	135	30.0%
Honeymoon	6	1.3%	2	0.4%	8	1.8%
Health	8	1.8%	7	1.6%	15	3.3%
Adventure	24	5.3%	1	0.2%	25	5.6%
Visiting Friends & Relatives	6	1.3%	1	0.2%	7	1.6%
Cultural & Historical	2	0.4%	45	10.0%	47	10.4%
Others	3	0.7%	3	0.7%	6	1.3%
Total	341	75.8%	109	24.2%	450	100.0%

Foreign visitors tended to remain for three to five nights before returning home after a week, but most Indian tourists stayed for two or three nights, as seen in the table and figure below. 8.2% of the visitors were foreign nationals, and the breakdown was as follows: 19.3% were Indian, staying for 1-2 nights; 19.1% for 1 week; 8.2% for 3-5 nights; and 6% for 1 week. The smallest contributor was day visitors, with 7.6%; of these, 6.2% were Indian and 1.3% were tourists from other countries. Another striking statistic is that 75.7% of visitors remained anywhere from one night to one week, as seen clearly in the table.

Table 8: Comparison of Nationality and Duration of Stay

Characteristic/ Profile	Indian		Foreigner		Total	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
Day visitor	28	6.2%	6	1.3%	34	7.6%
1-2 nights	87	19.3%	23	5.1%	110	24.4%
3-5 nights	81	18.0%	37	8.2%	118	26.2%
1 week	86	19.1%	27	6.0%	113	25.1%
More than 1 week	59	13.1%	16	3.6%	75	16.7%
Total	341	75.8%	109	24.2%	450	100.0%

Half of the respondents (or 50.0%), 182 of whom were Indian and 43 of whom were foreigners, visited Jammu and Kashmir with their families, according to the table and figure shown below. This further proved that families make up the bulk of the state's tourist population. The next largest category, with 25.6% of responses, were tourists travelling with friends. This group included 20.2% Indians and 5.3% international visitors. Jammu and Kashmir was the chosen destination for 19.1% of visitors travelling with a spouse. Travellers coming alone had the smallest impact, accounting for only 2.0% of the total. On the given surveys, 3.3% chose "others" as their answer, therefore concealing the identity of their visitors.

Table 9: Nationality versus Travel Agent(s)

Characteristic/ Profile	Indian		Foreigner		Total	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
Alone	8	1.8%	1	0.2%	9	2.0%
Spouse	52	11.6%	34	7.6%	86	19.1%
Family	182	40.4%	43	9.6%	225	50.0%
Friends	91	20.2%	24	5.3%	115	25.6%
Others	8	1.8%	7	1.6%	15	3.3%
Total	341	75.8%	109	24.2%	450	100.0%

In order to raise awareness among prospective tourists, promotional techniques that make use of various promotional media are effective. If the advertising effort is substantial enough, it may persuade prospective tourists to become real tourists. Therefore, using a Likert scale from 0 (not at all) to 5 (very much), we asked participants to indicate how much they knew and were motivated by the various promotional tactics. No Extent was given the value 1, Small Extent the value 2, Some Extent the value 3, Large Extent the value 4, and Very Large Extent the value 5. Various promotional tools were ranked according to their effectiveness by calculating the mean of the supplied values.

Table 10: Distribution of Promotional Strategies' Means and Standard Deviations

S. No.	Statements	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Rank	Std. Deviation
1	Online marketing	450	3	5	4.24	1	0.551
2	Promotional Events, Trade Shows, and Billboards	450	3	5	4.04	2	0.398
3	Publicity via Newspaper	450	3	5	3.74	3	0.678
4	Movie Commercials	450	3	5	3.74	4	0.680
5	Personal Recommendation (Non-Digital)	450	3	5	3.73	5	0.651
6	Press Conference Advertising	450	3	5	3.73	6	0.666
7	Discounting Products to Promote Sales	450	3	5	3.73	7	0.649
8	Radio and Television Commercials	450	3	5	3.72	8	0.673
9	Interviews for Publicity	450	3	5	3.72	9	0.639
10	Online Recommendation	450	3	5	3.71	10	0.669
11	Promotional Focus on Featured Articles	450	3	5	3.70	11	0.667
12	Marketing for Sales Using Money-Back Agencies	450	3	5	3.70	12	0.668
13	Promoting sales via Premium Offers	450	3	5	3.69	13	0.608
14	Promotion via One-Off Events (such as TTF)	450	3	5	3.67	14	0.580
15	Marketing by Travel Publications	450	3	5	3.67	15	0.596
16	Promoting Sales with Branded Souvenir	450	3	5	3.64	16	0.597
17	Promotional sales using coupons and discounts	450	3	5	3.56	17	0.532
18	Celebrity Endorsements	450	3	4	3.56	18	0.497
19	Promotional mailings	450	2	3	2.35	19	0.478
20	Marketing using Kiosk Direct	450	2	3	2.31	20	0.463
	Valid N (list wise)	450					

The data shown in the table above illustrates the average, ranking, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values of the 20 assertions pertaining to the various forms of tourist marketing. Based on their average worth, several kinds of promotional tools have been ranked. 'Advertising by Internet' gets the highest mean score at 4.24, while 'Advertising by Billboards, Trade exhibitions & Events' comes in second with a mean score of 4.04. "Direct marketing by kiosk" has the lowest mean score at 2.31 and "Direct marketing by mail" has the second-lowest score at 2.35. "So, it's safe to say that direct marketing didn't do much to raise awareness among prospective tourists or promote tourism in Jammu and Kashmir. The success of the campaign as a whole depends on well-managed direct marketing. The other methods, in addition to direct promotion, were successful in raising enough awareness and enthusiasm among prospective visitors to warrant a mean score ranging from 4.24 to 3.56 (very much to very much).

Conclusion

The present study provides valuable insights into the demographic profile, travel preferences, and promotional influences shaping tourism in Jammu and Kashmir. It is evident that the majority of the region's tourists are domestic, educated, and primarily traveling for leisure or religious purposes. Family-oriented travel dominates the visitor landscape, and most tourists opt for short to medium-length stays. The findings highlight a significant gender skew toward male travelers and a concentration of visitors in the 26–45 age bracket. Notably, promotional strategies leveraging digital platforms, such as online marketing and trade events, were identified as the most effective in influencing travel decisions, whereas traditional direct marketing methods such as kiosk displays and postal mail had minimal impact. These insights underline the importance of data-driven,

targeted marketing and the necessity of aligning tourism policies with the evolving preferences and profiles of visitors. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the need for inclusive tourism development strategies that can cater to diverse demographic segments, thereby boosting the sustainable growth of the tourism sector in Jammu and Kashmir.

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